

KINESTHETIC STRATEGY AS A TOOL FOR ENHANCING STEM LEARNING: ADDRESSING COGNITIVE STYLES IN SECONDARY EDUCATION

BY

UMAR AMINA SALIHU¹, MUHAMMAD MAIMUNA MADAKI² & JIBRIL JAMILA³

Department of Science Education, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria¹

email: aminasalihuumar2224@gmail.com.

Phone: 08068017344 (Correspondence)

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Abstract

This study focused on "Enhancing STEM Learning through Kinaesthetic Strategies for different Cognitive learners in Secondary Education". Despite increasing emphasis on STEM education to prepare students for a rapidly evolving workforce, many secondary school learners struggle to achieve optimal performance in science subjects like biology due to mismatches between teaching methods and their individual cognitive styles. The study adopted a quasi-experimental control group design, involving aprettest, and aposttest. The population comprised 6,346 SSII Biology students from 15 public co-education senior secondary schools in Giwa Education Zone, Kaduna, Nigeria. 120 students from two schools participated in the study. Impulsive and Reflective Student Scale (IRSS), with a reliability coefficient of 0.82, was used to establish the cognitive style of the student. The Ecology Concept Performance Test (ECPT), with a reliability coefficient of 0.88, was used to measure the academic performance of students. The reliability of the ECPT and IRSS were determined using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) after test-retest method was applied. The experimental group was taught using kinesthetic strategy while the control group was taught using a conventional method. Two research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation statistics, and two null hypotheses were tested at $p \leq 0.05$. Data collected were analysed using an independent t-test, one-way ANOVA and Scheffe's test. Results among others revealed that: a significant difference exists between the mean performance score of the experimental and control groups ($P = 0.001 < 0.05$). Based on these findings, it was concluded that the kinesthetic strategy enhanced students' academic performance, which was attributed largely to the positive learning environment offered by the strategy. Kinesthetic strategy also helps narrow performance gaps between these cognitive styles, making STEM education more inclusive. The study recommends that the kinesthetic strategy should be integrated into education in everyday activities to make learning more accessible, engaging, and effective for students, helping them develop essential skills practically and enjoyably. Workshops and seminars should be conducted to update teachers on how to effectively teach using the kinesthetic strategy.

Keywords: STEM education, kinesthetic strategy, cognitive styles, impulsive learners, reflective learners.

Introduction

STEM education, encompassing science, technology, engineering, and mathematics has become increasingly vital in equipping students with the knowledge and skills necessary for success in a rapidly evolving, technology-driven global economy. The National Science Board(2020) noted that as industries transform through automation, artificial intelligence, biotechnology, and other emerging technologies, there is a growing demand for a workforce proficient in critical thinking, problem-solving,

collaboration, and innovation. STEM education fosters these competencies by promoting inquiry-based learning, scientific literacy, and real-world application of concepts. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2019) noted that many developing and developed countries, including Nigeria, reported persistent concern about students' low performance and engagement in STEM subjects, particularly at the secondary school level, where foundational skills for advanced study and careers are established. Addressing these challenges requires not only curriculum reforms

but also instructional strategies that recognise diverse learning styles and cognitive profiles, ensuring that all students can access and excel in STEM education. Enhancing the effectiveness of STEM instruction is therefore critical for both individual career readiness and national competitiveness in the global economy.

Engaging diverse learners in STEM education presents several challenges, particularly when addressing cognitive diversity. Cognitive diversity, according to Kagan, (1965), is the varying ways in which students process, interpret, and respond to information, often categorised as impulsive or reflective cognitive styles. Riding and Rayner (2013) further explained that Impulsive learners tend to respond quickly to stimuli, often prioritising speed over accuracy, while reflective learners take more time to analyse information before making decisions. Moreover, STEM subjects typically require a high level of abstract thinking and problem-solving, which can be more challenging for students with diverse cognitive styles. Programme for International Students Assessment [PISA] (2018) noted that this may create an environment where students who do not fit the “standard” cognitive mould may become disengaged or frustrated, leading to lower motivation and academic performance. Meanwhile, OECD (2019) reported that teachers may lack the resources or knowledge to tailor instruction to the varying needs of their students, further exacerbating these disparities. Incorporating more active and differentiated teaching strategies according to Cheney (2017), such as a kinesthetic-learning strategy, may help bridge this gap by accommodating different cognitive styles, particularly impulsive and reflective, and encouraging more engaged, hands-on learning experiences for all students. However, Darling-Hammond et al. (2017) noted that the lack of teacher training and support in these areas remains a significant barrier to

effectively addressing cognitive diversity in STEM classrooms.

Kinesthetic-learning strategy, refers to an educational approach in which students learn through physical activities, rather than through passive listening or watching (Cheney 2017). This strategy involves engaging students in hands-on activities that require movement, manipulation, and interaction with objects or materials, promoting learning through physical experiences. For instance, in a biology lesson, students may act out processes such as photosynthesis, construct models of cell structures, or participate in science experiments to better understand abstract concepts. Research from Fleming and Mills (1992) has shown that the kinesthetic-learning strategy enhances engagement and retention, as it taps into the brain’s natural processes of memory and motor coordination. By engaging the body, kinesthetic strategies help students' process information in a multi-sensory manner, which can be particularly beneficial for students who struggle with traditional, text-heavy learning formats. A study by Umar (2015) has also highlighted that kinesthetic-learning improves critical thinking and problem-solving skills by encouraging active participation and experimentation. In secondary education, Baker and Thomas (2016) have proven that the kinesthetic-learning strategy improved student motivation and participation, particularly in practical subjects like Biology and Chemistry. In the context of STEM education, kinesthetic strategies can be particularly effective in helping students connect theory to practice, making complex scientific concepts more tangible and accessible. This approach also fosters collaboration and teamwork, as students often work together on projects and experiments, which enhances their interpersonal and communication skills, a key competency in the future workforce.

The significance of this study lies in its potential to inform both educational theory and practice by addressing a crucial gap in current STEM pedagogy. While existing research has highlighted the benefits of kinesthetic-learning in general, few studies have examined its application within the context of cognitive style differences (impulsive vs. reflective learners) in secondary STEM education. By tailoring instructional strategies to meet the diverse cognitive needs of students, this paper aims to demonstrate how the kinesthetic-learning strategy can help close performance gaps, foster greater student engagement, and equip learners with the skills required for success in STEM fields. Moreover, the findings could have broader implications for improving STEM education policies and practices, ensuring that all students, regardless of cognitive style, are prepared for the future workforce.

The theoretical framework upon which this study was based is the dual-process theory of Evans (2008), which is a review of Kagan's (1965) Matching Familiar Figures Test (MFFT). Kagan's theory posits that these cognitive styles are not necessarily linked to intelligence but to individual preferences for how information is processed. According to Kagan, impulsive learners tend to act more quickly but may be less accurate, while reflective learners are slower but more accurate. The dual-process theory (Evans, 2008) further builds on this by suggesting that cognitive processing can be categorised into two systems: a fast, automatic, impulsive system and a slow, deliberate, reflective system. In education, it implies that students may benefit from teaching strategies tailored to their cognitive style, which may influence their learning effectiveness.

Statement of the Problem

STEM education, comprising science, technology, engineering, and mathematics is

essential for preparing students to thrive in an increasingly complex, technology-driven global society. The National Research Council, (2011) states that STEM education cultivates critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and problem-solving skills, which are foundational for innovation and economic competitiveness. Moreover, the World Economic Forum, (2020) noted that as industries rapidly evolve due to advancements in artificial intelligence, automation, and biotechnology, the demand for a workforce equipped with STEM competencies continues to rise. Despite this growing need, Umar (2024) reported that many secondary school students underperform or disengage from STEM subjects due to traditional instructional approaches that fail to accommodate diverse learning needs. This presents a barrier not only to individual academic success but also to broader workforce development and national progress. Integrating more inclusive, student-centred teaching strategies is therefore crucial for ensuring equitable access to STEM opportunities and for building a future-ready workforce. Kinesthetic-learning strategy can help close performance gaps, foster greater student engagement, and equip learners with the skills like collaboration and teamwork for success in STEM fields.

Objectives of the Study

This study was guided by the following research objectives which are to;

1. Determine the effects of the Kinesthetic-learning strategy on the academic performance of SSII students taught ecology concepts.
2. Determine the effects of the Kinesthetic-learning strategy on the academic performance of SSII impulsive and reflective students taught ecology concepts.

Research Questions

Based on the objectives stated, the study sought answers to the following questions.

1. What is the difference between the mean performance score of SSII students taught ecology concepts using the Kinesthetic-learning strategy and those taught using the conventional method?
2. What is the difference between the mean performance score of SSII impulsive and reflective students taught ecology concepts using the Kinesthetic-learning strategy and those taught using the conventional method?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance.

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of SSII students taught ecology concepts using the Kinesthetic-learning strategy and those taught using the conventional method.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of SSII impulsive and reflective students taught ecology concepts using the Kinesthetic-learning strategy and those taught using the conventional method.

Methodology

The study adopted a quasi-experimental control group design. The population of this study was made up of all 6,346 SSII biology students, 3,762 males and 2,584 females, all from Public senior secondary schools within the Giwa Education Zone of Kaduna state. A simple random sampling technique by balloting was employed to select four co-education schools from the 15 senior secondary schools in Giwa Education Zone. In each of these four schools, one intact class was further randomly selected and subjected to an equivalent test; to find out two schools that are not statistically different in ability. Two schools were finally selected and randomly assigned to experimental and control groups. Two research instruments were used to generate data in this study: the Impulsive

Reflective Student Scale (IRSS) and the Ecology Concept Performance Test (ECPT).

Students in both experimental and control groups were subjected to IRSS to determine impulsive and reflective students in each of the groups before commencement of the treatment. Using Kegan's (1966) MFFT samples, the researcher adapted the framework and developed 10 similar test items named IRSS to suit SSII students. The rule of the task is that, students are shown a familiar image (standard) and six similar variants. Only one of the variants is identical to the standard. The students are asked to select the variant that is identical to match the standard. The score is the average of the number of errors and response time to the first selection across the total number of test items. Students with below-median errors and above-median response times were classified as reflective, while those with above-median errors and below-median response times were deemed impulsive. The experimental group was made up of 34 impulsive and 21 reflective students. The control group was made up of 44 and 21 impulsive and reflective students.

The Ecology Concept Performance Test (ECPT) was adapted from previous Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSCE) questions. It is made up of 42 questions. A total of 42 items comprising 32 multiple choice items with options A-D, one answer and three distracters, including 10 fill-in-the-blank. ECPT was administered as a pretest and posttest to establish the effects of the treatment on performance. These instruments were subjected to both face and content validity. The face validity was done by senior lecturers who are experts in test/evaluation in the Faculty of Education, and they reviewed items for clarity and suitability of language to the target respondents. The reliability of the instrument yielded a PPMCC of 0.82 and 0.88 for IRSS and ECPT respectively. Descriptive statistics were

employed in the analysis of the data collected. All research questions earlier stated were answered using mean and standard deviation, while the hypotheses were tested using t-test, one-way ANOVA, as well as post hoc Scheffe's test at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance.

Result

Data obtained for this study were analysed based on the research questions as follows:

Table 1 Mean and Standard Deviation in Experimental and Control Groups

Groups	N	Mean	STD	Mean difference
Experimental	55	26.75	3.38	2.65
Control	65	24.11	3.56	
Total	120			

1. What is the difference between the mean performance score of SSII students taught ecology concepts using the Kinesthetic-learning strategy and those taught using the conventional method?

To answer research question two, Mean and standard deviation were used on ECPT, and a summary of statistics is presented in Table 1.

The result of the descriptive statistics from Table 1 revealed the difference between the mean performance scores of students in the experimental and control groups. The descriptive mean statistic revealed the mean performance score of the experimental group to be 26.75 and the control group to be 24.11, with a mean difference of 2.65. This clearly indicates that the experimental group have a higher mean performance score than the control group. To test whether the difference was significant or not,

Table 2: t-test statistic on the difference in the mean performance of the experimental and control groups

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	STD	Mean diff.	Df	T cal.	T crit.	p-value
mean performance	Experimental	55	26.75	3.38	2.65	186	5.20	1.96	0.001
	Control	60	24.11	3.56					

null hypothesis one was tested and result is presented in Table 2

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of SSII students taught ecology concepts using the Kinesthetic-learning strategy and those taught using the conventional method.

To test null hypothesis one, an independent t-test was employed on ECPT, and a summary of the analysis is presented in Table 2

p value – 0.001 < 0.05, t computed = 5.204 > .96 at df 186

Results of the independent t-test statistics revealed a significant difference in the mean performance of the experimental and control

groups. Reasons being that the p-value calculated of 0.001 is lower than the 0.05 alpha level, and its computed t-value of 5.204 is greater than the 1.96 t critical value at df 186. Therefore the null hypothesis is rejected

2. What is the difference between the mean performance score of SSII impulsive and reflective students taught ecology concepts using the Kinesthetic-learning strategy and those taught using the conventional method?

To answer research question two, mean and standard deviation were used on the ECPT posttest, and a summary of statistics is presented in Table 3

Table 3: Means and Standard Deviation of Performance in Experimental and Control Groups.

Cognitive Group styles	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean difference
Reflective Experimental	21	28.64	2.30	4.62
Control	20	24.02	3.60	
Impulsive Experimental	34	25.08	3.35	1.01
Control	44	24.07	3.59	

The result of the descriptive statistics from Table 3 revealed the difference between the mean performance scores of impulsive and reflective students in the experimental and control groups. The descriptive mean statistic revealed that the mean performance score of reflective students in the experimental and control groups is 28.64 and 24.02, with a mean difference of 4.62, while impulsive students in the experimental and control groups have 25.08 and 24.07 mean scores, with a difference of 1.01. This clearly shows that based on cognitive styles (Reflective and Impulsive), the experimental group have a higher mean performance score than the control

group. To test whether the difference was significant or not, null hypothesis two was tested, and the summary of the results is presented in Table 4.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of SSII impulsive and reflective students taught ecology concepts using the Kinesthetic-learning strategy and those taught using a conventional method.

To test null hypothesis two, one-way ANOVA was employed, and a summary of the analysis is presented in Table 4

Table 4: ANOVA Distribution on Performance of Students in Experimental and Control Groups

Variables	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F crit.	P R value
Between Groups	332.03	3	110.68	9.76	.00 sig
Within Groups	1303.51	115	11.33		
Total	1635.55	118			

P = 0.000 < 0.05, F computed = 9.764 > 3.00 F critical at df 3, 115, R=remark

From Table 4, the outcome of the Analysis of Variance shows that the calculated P-value 0.00 is lower than the alpha value 0.05 level of significance, and the computed F value of 9.76 is above the 3.000 F critical value at df 3. This

implies that significant differences exist between the mean performance scores of SSII impulsive and reflective students in the experimental and control groups in favour of the experimental group. Consequently, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference

between the mean performance scores of SSII impulsive and reflective students taught ecology concepts using the Kinesthetic-learning strategy and those taught using the conventional method,

is hereby rejected. To reveal the groups with a significant difference, a post hoc Scheffe’s test was used, the result is presented in Table 5

Table 5: Multiple Comparison of Students’ Performance in Experimental and Control Groups

(I) Groups of Cognitive Styles	(J) Groups of Cognitive Styles	N	Mean	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	P Value	Remark
Experimental Reflective	Experimental Impulsive	34	25.08	3.55*	.93	.003	Sig
	Control Reflective	20	24.02	4.61*	1.05	.000	Sig
	Control Impulsive	44	24.07	4.56*	.89	.000	Sig
	Experimental Reflective	21	28.64	-3.55*	.93	.003	Sig
Experimental Impulsive	Control Reflective	20	24.02	1.06	.94	.740	N S
	Control Impulsive	44	24.07	1.00	.76	.633	N S
Control Reflective	Experimental Reflective	21	28.64	-4.61*	1.05	.000	Sig
	Experimental Impulsive	34	25.08	-1.06	.94	.740	N S
	Control Impulsive	44	24.07	-.05	.90	1.00	N S
Control Impulsive	Experimental Reflective	21	28.08	-4.56*	.89	.000	Sig
	Experimental Impulsive	34	25.08	-1.00	.76	.633	N S
	Control Reflective	20	24.02	.054	.90	1.00	N S

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 5 post hoc Scheffe’s mean comparison test indicates significant differences exist between the mean performance score of SSII impulsive and reflective students in the experimental and control groups. The post hoc Scheffe’s means comparison clearly indicates that the P values calculated 0.03, 0.00 and 0.00 are lower than the P value 0.05, which implies that a significant difference exists between the mean performance scores of experimental reflective, experimental impulsive, and control impulsive in favour of experimental reflective. While the P calculated 0.740, 0.633 and 1.00 is higher than the P value 0.05, which implies that no significant difference in the mean performance scores between experimental impulsive, control reflective and control impulsive.

Discussion of Findings

Findings revealed a significant difference in the mean performance scores between the experimental group taught ecology concepts using the Kinesthetic-learning strategy and the control group taught the same concepts using the conventional method. The difference was in favour of the experimental groups. This finding suggests that the kinesthetic-learning strategy has a positive effect on academic performance in ecology concepts at the senior secondary level. Kinesthetic-learning strategies promote greater interaction between students and teachers. Teachers observed and provided real-time feedback during hands-on activities, which benefited learners who needed immediate reinforcement and also provided opportunities to

discuss and analyse the hands-on activities, helping them to build deeper insights. The finding agrees with other studies like Solomon et al. (2023), Ameyaw et al. (2018), Boone, (2016) and Umar (2015). All reported positive effects of the kinesthetic-learning strategy on academic performance when compared to the conventional method.

The results also revealed a significant difference in the mean performance scores between the experimental group taught ecology concepts using the kinesthetic-learning strategy and the control group taught the same concepts using the conventional method. The difference was in favour of experimental groups to be precise, reflective and impulsive students taught with the Kinesthetic-learning strategy. Impulsive learners showed significant improvements in their performance after participating in kinesthetic activities. This suggests that hands-on, quick-feedback strategies help them focus and enhance their understanding of biological concepts. Their tendency to make fast decisions may be complemented by the immediate engagement and action-oriented nature of the kinesthetic-learning strategy. While reflective learners demonstrate improved performance, this suggests that kinesthetic-learning provides them with an opportunity for deeper engagement and time for thoughtful reflection while still involving movement and hands-on tasks. This deliberative approach allows them to connect abstract concepts with tangible experiences. Integrating kinesthetic activities into secondary STEM curricula, especially in biology is crucial. Teachers can adopt strategies that involve physical activities, role-playing, and simulations to enhance students' understanding of complex scientific concepts. This aligns with recent calls for more interactive and experiential learning in STEM. Kinesthetic-learning strategy provides a versatile approach that caters to diverse cognitive styles, promoting active participation for both impulsive and reflective students.

Conclusion

The following conclusions were deduced from this study

1. Kinesthetic-learning strategy helped students build problem-solving skills, which are essential for the future workforce. It actively engages students with real-world problems, such as biological experiments or ecological challenges, preparing them for future roles in STEM fields. Students learned how to analyse, synthesise, and apply scientific concepts to solve problems, a crucial skill for future careers in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics.
2. Kinesthetic-learning strategy often involves group work and collaborative problem-solving. By working together on biology experiments, model-building tasks, or simulations, students developed collaborative skills, such as teamwork, communication, and negotiation. These soft skills are highly valued in the modern workforce, where employees need to collaborate across diverse teams and communicate complex ideas effectively.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made from this study

1. Senior secondary school teachers could be sensitised by professional bodies like the Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) through workshops, conferences, and symposia on the use of the Kinesthetic-learning strategy in learning science (Ecology/Biology).
2. School administrators like principals and senior masters should perpetually encourage and support biology teachers in providing resources (or improvising) and using the Kinesthetic-learning strategy to facilitate classroom explorations and hands-on learning.

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